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"I Didn't Hear That!"

They say my wife's a teacher, proud,
She lectures strong, she lectures loud.
But I'm the student, brave and bold
Who somehow missed what I was told.

She talks from breakfast 'til we sleep,
About the bills, the floor, the jeep.
I nod along, my face looks wise,
But truth be told... I fantasize.

I hear her voice like background hum,
While I dream of snacks and chewing gum.
She says, "Did you take out the trash?"
I blink, "You told me that?" *Oh, flash!*

She gives me lists, she makes a chart,
She speaks like love's a kind of art.
But all I hear is "blah blah blah"
And then the word "Shopee" or "Ma!"

One day she said, "Let's have a quiz."
I panicked fast, "*Oh no, what's this?*"
"What did I say last night at ten?"
I froze. *Was it about the pen?*

I flunked the test, but passed the charm,
I smiled and gave her flowers (farm).
She rolled her eyes, said, "Nice try, dear."
Then hugged me close and pulled me near.

She teaches love, not just the chores,
And though I miss a few "lessons" (more),
This classroom life I wouldn't swap,
She's teacher, queen and I'm her flop.

So, if you ask what marriage is,
Its love wrapped up in pop quizzes.
And me? I'm learning... bit by bit
Even if I "didn't hear it."

